

Introduction

The assessment of land cover changes and their influence on ecosystem support services (ESS) is a useful tool for decision makers as it offers foundational insights into regional dynamics and ecological changes. The following instructions give an overview on the data, software and analytical steps required to perform an assessment of ecosystem service supply (ESSS), adapted by the methodology of Burkhard et al. (2012). ESSS is the capacity of a region to provide a range of ecological resources and services, e.g. water purification and biodiversity through forest or urban land cover, within a specific time period (Burkhard et al., 2012).

Data & software requirements

Data

The assessment of ESSS relies on raster data, mainly in the form of land classification. Such data is offered by numerous commercial providers and open data sources or can be created ad hoc using remote sensing data. The choice of land cover dataset is determined by the geographical scale, time periods and image resolution for the examined region. Typical data sources for satellite imagery and land cover data are given in the appendix.

Software

A GIS (Geographic Information System) is needed to process the spatial data and perform the ESSS assessment. Typical examples are the licensed *ArcGIS Pro Software* from ESRI or the open-source *QGIS*. These provide the necessary applications to read certain data types and implement functions to perform calculations on raster data.

Land Cover Classification

Before performing the ESSS assessment, land cover data must be created and pre-processed to reflect the spatial extent and time period under consideration. If there are no suitable datasets for the study area, one must be created from scratch, requiring remote sensing data at the desired resolution. Free sources usually offer data at resolution 10m to 30m, which is a sufficient level of detail for most regional scales. The selected classes of land use will later determine the quality of the ESSS. While the issue of creating a land cover classification is too complicated to be discussed here, there are many online resources and publications on how to perform easy but useful classifications. Some literature and references on land cover classification are given in the appendix.

Ecosystem Service Supply Assessment

Here the method of assessing ESSS is adapted from Burkhard et al. (2012). This is based on a scoring matrix derived from the European Corine Land Cover (CLC) nomenclature, which divides ground cover into five main classes: artificial surfaces, agricultural areas, forest and seminatural areas, wetlands and water bodies. Each category includes several more specific land cover types.

The scoring matrix must be adjusted to apply this nomenclature to individual land use data of the studied area. The detailed CLC classes can be unified into more simple categories, e.g. *broad-leaved forest*, *coniferous forest* and *mixed forest* into a general *forest*-class to reflect the land cover types classified in the dataset. For this, the respective matrix score is simply averaged across the combined

classes. **Note that generalizing the classes and scoring system will lead to less detailed results and a more superficial interpretation of the ESSS!**

Example of re-calculating the matrix score for a generalized “forest”-class from CLC-categories:

$$\text{Forest Class Score} = \frac{\text{broadleaved forest BiodiversityScore} + \text{coniferous forest BiodiversityScore} + \text{mixed forest BiodiversityScore}}{3}$$

The adjusted scoring matrix can be inserted into the attribute table of the land cover raster dataset. The desired ESS categories are added as additional columns to the table, assigning the respective score to each land cover type (Fig. 1). Subsequently, the newly assigned values can be mapped by selecting a specific attribute as the displayed layer (Fig. 2).

LandCover	Count	Biodiv	FloodProt	Recreation	Waterpurific
water	37610	4	1,5	5	1,5
forest	445501	4,5	3	5	5
grassland	6097	4	1	1,5	2,5
agriculture	213660	2,5	0,9	2,4	0,4
urban	110353	1,3	0	0,5	0,2
barren land	7354	3	3	4,5	0,5

Fig. 1: Attribute table of land cover dataset with assigned ESSS score for Biodiversity, Flood-Protection, Recreation and Water-Purification taken over from the scoring matrix

The overall score for a specific ESS in the image scene can be calculated by multiplying the number of each land cover type pixel by the matching ESSS score, summing these values and then dividing this sum by the total number of pixels:

$$\text{Overall Biodiversity Score} = \frac{(\text{ForestPixels} \times \text{ForestBiodiversityScore}) + (\text{WaterPixels} \times \text{WaterBiodiversityScore}) + (\text{UrbanPixels} \times \text{UrbanBiodiversityScore}) + \dots}{\text{Total Number of Pixels}}$$

(compare with Fig. 1)

Temporal changes in ESSS can be evaluated using raster calculation tools by subtracting the raster image of one year from that of another. The resulting image will show the scoring difference for each pixel.

Fig. 2: ESSS map of biodiversity (right) derived from land classification (left) using a 30mx30m resolution Landsat dataset

Literature on ESSS assessment

- Burkhard, B., Kroll, F., Müller, F., Windhorst, W., 2009. Landscapes' capacities to provide ecosystem services - A concept for land-cover based assessments. *Landsc. Online* 15–15. <https://doi.org/10.3097/LO.200915>
- Burkhard, B., Kroll, F., Nedkov, S., Müller, F., 2012. Mapping ecosystem service supply, demand and budgets. *Ecol. Indic.* 21, 17–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2011.06.019>
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Data sources for satellite imagery & land cover data

- **USGS-Earth Explorer**
30m Landsat-Satellite Imagery, Land Cover, Elevation Data
<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>
 - **Copernicus Browser**
10m Sentinel 2-Satellite Imagery
<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>
 - **ESRI Land Cover from Living Atlas of the World**
10m Sentinel 2-based Land Cover Data
<https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=cfc7609de5f478eb7666240902d4d3d>
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Literature & software tutorials on land cover classification

- **Step-by-Step: Land Cover Change Detection through Supervised Classification**
<https://www.un-spider.org/advisory-support/recommended-practices/recommended-practice-land-cover-change/step-by-step>
- **Land Use Land Cover Change Detection with Supervised Classification in QGIS**
https://dges.carleton.ca/CUOSGwiki/index.php/Land_Use_Land_Cover_Change_Detection_with_Supervised_classification_in_QGIS
- **Arset – Land Cover Classification with Satellite Imagery**
<https://appliedsciences.nasa.gov/get-involved/training/english/arset-land-cover-classification-satellite-imagery>

Authors:

Maximilian Haase, Wolfgang Wende & Suili Xiao

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER), Dresden, Germany

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